

DCH File Naming Worksheet

Version 1.0.0

This worksheet helps you to develop and document a file naming convention for your dataset. Good naming conventions are based on clear principles. Our principles for good naming conventions are described and explained in

Rau, F. (2023). *DCH File Naming Guidelines*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447484>

Rau, F. (2023). *DCH File Naming Recommendations*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447562>

We recommend that you follow these principles if you work with this worksheet.

Now let's put our five principles to work. With the following eight steps we will guide you through the process of defining and documenting your own file naming convention!

1. What set of files will your naming convention cover?

Define the scope of your naming pattern. Does it apply to your whole dataset or to a specific subset. How is that subset defined (e.g. data type, processing stage, function)? You can use different conventions for different file (sub)sets. Use one worksheet for a single (sub)set.

This worksheet will cover

2. What categories of information are important for your files?

The important aspect is, what distinguishes one file in your dataset from the other files in this dataset. What makes your dataset distinct from others is not important here.

Ideally, pick three categories of metadata. Don't use more than five. The pattern should be succinct enough so that you can visually scan the file names and easily understand the information contained in each one.

Example: For my recordings, I want to know language, participant, and date of recording. For my scans I want to know the book, volume, and page.

Name and list your categories here:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

3. Do these categories have an open or closed vocabulary?

For our purposes, there are two general categories of metadata. Open categories, where you cannot give a finite list of possible values and categories that are filled from a finite closed set of values.

Open categories can be completely open, however it is often possible to specify a pattern that all values of this category follow. Examples of truly open categories are titles of works. However, even in these cases, the actual list of possible values in a given data set might be finite and even short. For other categories, such as dates, we can give a well defined pattern how every possible value will be structured.

For finite lists, the next question is: Do you need to abbreviate the values to make the whole filename more succinct – and in many cases also more structured? For some categories such as languages (ISO 639), countries (ISO 3166) , writing systems (ISO 15924) there are widely used vocabularies such as the two letter codes of ISO 639-1 standard for major languages (e.g. English *en*, French *fr*) or its corresponding three letter code for most languages (English *eng*, Cambodian *khm*, Skwxwú7mesh sníchim *sqn*). Standardized codes have the advantage that the field has a predictable length and that the values are generally restricted to basic latin letters and/or arabic numbers.

If you are using a not widely used and/or not publicly documented vocabulary, you should provide a documentation of the vocabulary in your naming pattern documentation. This is particularly important for dataset specific vocabularies (such as participant codes).

If you need to indicate structure inside a single category, use the hyphen - to separate the parts inside the category. (Example: If your location information consists of a country and additional administrative level 1 information, you should separate them

with a hyphen, so that the state Wyoming in the USA would be represented as *US-WY* which is also a valid ISO-3166-2 code.

Give the type (open/closed), patterns, and/or type of vocabulary here:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

4. What is the order for the metadata in the file name?

Now is the time to fix the order of your categories. Remember: Files are often ordered alphabetically (read from left to right) when displayed as a list. This means that the left-most category provides the first level of ordering and the second category order inside the first category, and so on.

(Do the patterns inside the individual categories facilitate sorting inside the category? The most important case are dates, where you should always follow the YYYY-MM-DD pattern.)

Example 1: Books are the top level of ordering, followed by volume, and pages.

Finalize your order here:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

5. Will you need to track different versions of each file?

You can track versions of a file by appending version information to the end of the file name. Consider using a simple version number (e.g. *v01*) or the version date (use ISO 8601 format:YYYY-MM-DD or YYYYMMDD). Another possible vocabulary can be processing states (e.g. *_raw*, *_processed*, or any other state you identify in your workflow).

Versioning information: _____

6. Write down your complete naming convention pattern.

You now have your ordered one to five categories, you have specified the form each category can take. The categories should be separated by underscores. (Inside the categories separation is done with the hyphen, see step 3 above.)

Write down you pattern here, with labels for your categories

_____ - _____ - _____ - _____ - _____

Now write it down the pattern again, but replace the labels with a representation of the pattern in the category i.e. replace DATE with YYYY-MM-DD or ISO 639-3 LANGUAGE CODE with abc. Ideally, a full file name will be 32 characters or less.

7. Document this convention in a README file.

Create a text file (plain text or markdown) in an editor and document your naming pattern. Begin with a description of what dataset or subset this convention covers. For the documentation of the pattern start with the representations from step 6. After that define the categories one by one and document the vocabulary for each category (where applicable). Ideally you would end with one or two actual file names as examples and an explication for each of the names.

Keep the README file on (or next to) the top-level of your dataset.

The *DCH File Naming Worksheet* is based on Briney, Kristin A. 2020. "File Naming Convention Worksheet". <https://doi.org/10.7907/894q-zr22>. (CC-BY 4.0)

Cite as

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